

INSIGHT INTO RURAL POVERTY IN BANGLADESH

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(Abstract : The purpose of the present study is to enumerate the extent, and analyze the causes and consequences of the prevailing rural poverty; and the ways to get out of it. The study aims to accord both theoretical and empirical treatments to the issue of rural poverty. Especially, diverge theories of development and underdevelopment have been critically examined. An attempt has been made to examine the relevancy of different approaches so far as they relate to the alleviation of rural poverty in Bangladesh. It has been argued that all the approaches have some merits as well as limitations in explaining the rural poverty and suggesting the way out. The study is entirely based upon available secondary data. Empirical treatments have been based upon the findings of different studies carried out in Bangladesh. Specifically, the analysis of poverty trend project covering 62 villages conducted by the Bangladesh Institute of Development Studies (BIDS) in 1989-90 has been heavily relied upon.)

Introduction

The issue of rural poverty in Bangladesh is of paramount importance. It is not only because Bangladesh economy is predominantly agrarian in nature and 83.6 per cent of the population live in the rural areas, but also due to the fact the rural economy employs nearly 65 per cent of the total labor force. Bangladesh has a large population of 120 million within an area of 147,570 square kilometer. Considering the uni-dimensional indicator, nearly half of

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the rural population fall below the moderate poverty line. If we consider the case of extreme poverty, nearly one-third of the rural population fall below the line. However, if we consider the multi-dimensional indicators such as entitlement to decent housing, safe drinking water, sanitation, medicare, education and other social services provided by the state system, the proportion of the population living below the line must be much higher. There is no doubt that bringing this population above the line or at least reducing their number is the prime development imperative of Bangladesh. So the study of the issue of poverty in Bangladesh is undoubtedly worthwhile.

Defining Poverty

Understanding the concept of poverty is the first step toward study of poverty. However, there is no consensus among scholars as to the definition of poverty. Different authors define poverty differently. Poverty can be classified as primary poverty and secondary poverty. "Primary poverty is defined as the inability to command enough income (or expenditure) to buy the bare necessities of life. This poverty line is usually constructed by estimating the cost of a minimum diet of essential food items and the fuel needed to prepare it." [1] The concept of primary poverty focuses upon the lack of resources, on the part of the poor, to generate income. On the other hand, secondary poverty is defined "as a situation in which real incomes are adequate to buy the minimum needs basket, but for one reason or another (drink, gambling and inefficient housekeeping) the poor do not spend the money on satisfying these needs." [2] Here, the problem is relating to the efficient use of available resources rather than the lack of resources.

The concept of poverty also can be defined from absolute and relative point of view. It is noteworthy that the World Bank defines poverty as

the inability to attain a minimal standard of living and differentiates it from inequality.[3] In this paper we will be concerned with primary or absolute poverty. Now, the question is how to measure the poverty line. Quite reasonably, it differs from country to country depending upon physical environment, including climatic conditions, food habit, etc.. One way of calculating the poverty line is estimating the cost of minimum needs diet, cost of cooking and non-food necessities. Usually, this method is based upon a minimum nutritional basket. However, different organizations offer different nutritional baskets. The BIDS survey has used Tk.4790 per person per year as the cut-off line of moderate poverty which provides for a calorie intake of 2112 per capita per day derived from a food intake of 832 grams including consumption of 48 grams of fish, 12 gram of meat, 20 gram of oil and 20 gram of sugar per capita per day. It also provides for 30 per cent additional expenditure for meeting non-food basic needs. The cut-off line for extreme poor has been fixed at Tk. 2810 per capita per year providing for the calorie intake of 1740 per capita per day which is 80 per cent of the required quantity for moderate poverty.[4] This cut-off line is calculated for each adult-equivalent, because children require less amount of calorie. Thereby, it becomes possible to identify the gap between actual consumption and required consumption for each member of the household. The next step is to find out the number of people falling below the line and the ratio of this population to the total population. This ratio is termed as head count ratio and is widely used to measure the extent of poverty. One step further is the calculation of "income (consumption) gap measure" by which the proportion of the average income-gap of the poor population to the poverty line is measured.

Consumption-based calculation of poverty line provides an unidirectional measurement which does not depict the accurate picture of poverty. That is why, World Bank supplements the consumption-based poverty measure with nutrition, life expectancy, under 5 mortality, and school enrolment rates.[5] BIDS also adopted multi-

dimensional approach combining income and non-income measure such as nutrition, living environment, security, crisis coping capacity and participation. This approach helps us to understand poverty not only as a state but also as a process.[6] Now we would examine the extent of poverty in Bangladesh.

Extent of Poverty

There are a very few scientific studies conducted to measure the extent of poverty in Bangladesh. The government occasionally conducts the household expenditure and usually these are the basis for further research. A few individual researchers have tried to measure the poverty by micro study at the field level. However, the most significant study has been undertaken by BIDS which covers 62 villages in 57 districts (out of 64). It has been considered as base-work for further research and analysis of trend. Binayak Sen has calculated the percentage of population in poverty based on uniform method of the per capita expenditure classification. These figures show a spectacular decline in poverty over time although the situation is worse than neighbouring countries like Pakistan, Sri Lanka and India. However, many scholars challenge the arithmetic of poverty reduction in Bangladesh. Ravallion maintains that the decline of poverty in the 1980s is unconvincing. He argues that the rate of growth in real consumption per capita of 10 percent per year implied by the HES is too high to be believed. He maintains that the proportion of the population deemed to be poor has remained fairly stable over recent years, while absolute numbers of poor have increased.[7] In this regard, the findings of the BIDS survey (table-01) seems to be more convincing.

Table-01: Head Count Ratio (1987 and 1989-90)

	Extreme Poverty	Moderate and
Extreme Poverty		
1987-88	25.8	60.1
1989-90	27.5	55.4

Source: Mahabub Hossain (1995)[8]

Considering the quality of life indicators, the same survey finds that 17 percent of the households do not possess minimum clothing while the percentage is 30 for landless people; 24 percent having vulnerable housing; 91 percent do not have access to sanitary toilets; 24 percent do not possess any foot wear while the percentage is 44 for the landless group; and 87 percent do not have access to public health care system. However, 87 percent of the households have access to safe drinking water.[9]

Causes of Poverty

The causes of poverty can be traced in the socio-economic characteristics of the poor which have been discussed below:

Landlessness

The majority of the rural poor belong to the landless and functionally landless categories. Ravallion (1989) finds that 93 percent of the population owning no land and owning upto 0.5 acres land are poverty stricken.[10] The BIDS survey finds that the incidence of poverty is 78 percent for land less and 71 percent for marginal land owners. The survey also finds that among different occupational groups, the cultivator households have the minimum incidence of poverty. It also finds that share-cropping through the tenancy market does not contribute to reduction of poverty due to unequal share-cropping arrangements which benefits the land owner most.

Lack of Education

The incidence of poverty is endemic in the households whose head is illiterate. The level of education has been found negatively correlated with the incidence of poverty. The BIDS survey finds that the incidence of poverty is about 69 percent for households whose head had no formal schooling compared to only 27 percent for household heads who passed secondary schools. But the dropouts from the secondary level have no impact on earning capabilities. Education has been found effective for enhanced earning if associated with ownership of land.

Agricultural and Non-agricultural Wage-laborer

Since the most of the poverty stricken people possess no land or cultivable land, their only asset is labor. They mostly work as wage-laborers. The BIDS survey finds that about 85 percent of the population in wage-labor households are poor. However, the non-agricultural wage laborers are better-off than agricultural wage-laborer. Households with some capital for non-farm activities and having some skills are better-off than wage-labourers.

Decreasing Real Wages

The cause of poverty among the wage-laborers is due to the decreasing trend of real wages. A World Bank study in 1984 finds that despite sharp increase in the nominal agricultural wages, the real wages in 1982-83 was Tk. 5.87 taking 1973-74 wages of Tk. 6.69 as the base. According to the same calculation the real wages in 1969-70 was Tk. 7.58. On the other hand, the rural cost of living index has rose from 100 in 1969-70 to 744 in 1982-83.[11] Osmani also shows that the index of rice-exchange rate of wages risen upto 117 in 1985-86 from the base of 100 in 1973-74 although it was 119 in 1969-70.[12]

Hence it is clear that the declining trend of real wages against the sharp rising of cost of living index have been forcing the poor to live below the poverty level.

Unemployment and Under-employment

The majority of the poor are either unemployed or underemployed. This is due to massive increase in the labor force which in turn caused by the population boom in the 1970s. But the economy has failed to grow sufficiently to absorb additional labor force; thus, causing unemployment and underemployment. Although the population growth has been contained, to some extent, yet those who will join the labor force by the next two decades are already born. So the situation will remain the same unless the economy grows in a much faster rate.

Higher Dependency Ratio

It has been observed that the dependency ratio among the poor is much higher than the non-poor. Although rearing children is expensive, and the poor do not have sufficient resources for investment upon the children, yet the poor tend to have more children. The rationale is complex. World Bank maintains that, on the part of the poor, "the decision to have many children can be sensible response to poverty. Mortality is high for children in destitute families, but it is essential to ensure that some children survive to support the household in the parents' old age, if not sooner." [13] In addition, children can relieve the parents from many domestic tasks. In a society where child labor is the reality, it is not a surprise that the poor want to have more children.

Poor Health Care

Most of the poor do not have access to the public health care system. Because of malnutrition, they are very much prone to disease.

Especially the diarrhoeal diseases, asthma, typhoid, tuberculosis, etc. cause their early death or reduce their physical strength to do hard work. All these lead to more poverty of the dependants.

Natural Disaster

Bangladesh is very much prone to natural disasters such as flood, cyclone, drought and river bank erosion. Hye argues that natural disasters contribute to rural poverty in two ways: through destruction of food stock and whatever meagre assets the household on the margin of poverty have and by making employment opportunities scarce.[14]

Exploitation by Rural Elites

The rural society is dominated by the elites. They usually comprise of land-owning and educated class. Most of the government projects targeted towards the poorest people are channelled through the concerned Union Council, a local government body. The chairman of the Union Council and ward members are the most influential elites in the rural areas. Although they are elected representatives, they always act against the interest of the poor. Sometimes, the poor is bound to repay the loan which he never borrowed, and at the same time, he has to borrow from informal money lenders at an exacerbated interest rate often as high as 100 percent. Hye maintains that "empowerment and conscientiation of the rural poor are also resisted by them [rural elite's], as experienced by some of the NGOs recently." [15]

Urban Biased Development

The development policies of the state are urban biased and mainly targeted towards rich and the middle class of the society. Whatever money is being invested in the rural sector, the benefits are accrued by the land owning classes. Until very recently, a little effort was made to alleviate poverty or to ensure equity-oriented growth.

Infra-structure and Technology

Rural infra-structure and diffusion of technology, viz., seed-fertilizer-water technology seems to have critical influence on the income earning capability of the rural poor. Especially, many studies have found positive correlation between electrification of a village and development of communication system, and reduction of poverty. New technology improves the condition of marginal and small farmers. It restricts downward mobility.

Consequences of Rural Poverty

Bangladesh economy has been growing, since its independence in 1971 upto 1985-86, at the rate of 4.4 percent per annum. The rate of growth was 3.3 percent for the two decades preceding independence. For the same period, per capita GDP growth has been quadrupled from just over 0.5 percent to around 2 percent per annum.[16] This means that demand for food should be increased and as such price of foodgrain should also increase. In reality, the real price of foodgrain has remained stable over the last decade. How can it happen? Osmani argues that, because of highly skewed nature of distribution of income, only the rich is getting incremental benefits from growth. As their demand for food is over-saturated and the poor does not have the capability to buy enough food, so the demand for food and consequent price-rise is not happening.[17] This indicates that number of population in the extreme poor category is increasing while there is a slight decrease in the moderately poor population.

From the above discussion, we can conclude that the prevailing mass poverty exercising the following influences on the national economy: Firstly, it is seriously inhibiting the growth of agricultural sector which contributes about 32 percent to the GDP.

Secondly, contribution of agriculture sector to the industrialization in terms of generating investable surpluses and providing market for industrial products has been seriously jeopardized.

Thirdly, It is responsible for the occupational shift of agricultural wage laborer to non-farm sectors, although according to the concept of Lewisian turning point, the surplus labor should be absorbed by the manufacturing sector. (in fact, Lewis mentions capitalist sector which in Bangladesh perspective can be deemed to be manufacturing sector). Unfortunately, the manufacturing sector is unable to absorb so much unskilled and semi-skilled worker.

Fourthly, the massive occupational shift has resulted in loss of labor productivity in the non-farm sector. Osmani shows that in both the fast growing trade and construction sectors, labor absorption has progressed at a much faster rate than income, resulting in a precipitous fall in productivity. Particularly, trade has experienced a 59 percent fall in per capita income in the ten year period since 1974-75; whereas the percentage is a severe 86 in case of construction sector. As a result, the population engaged in non-farm sectors are equally poverty stricken.

Fifthly, rural poverty is the root cause of urban poverty. Unemployed and underemployed laborers migrating to the urban centers in search of employment, being unable to find any, they live in the slums, try to do something in the informal sector under the shadow of poverty. The most striking impact of urban poverty on rural poverty is that the former is exhausting the meagre resources of the government by attracting more investment in the urban public services; thus further pushing down the rural poverty.

Sixthly, poverty is responsible for rapid population growth. The poor is certainly aware of three facts of his life: (1) he will very soon lose his working capabilities and become dependent upon some one who

will take care of him; (2) the chance of survival of a child is totally uncertain; (3) the more children he has the more he will be secured in his days of inability, although he has to suffer during the child rearing years. Under such circumstances, the rationale choice for him is to have more children, and thereby compounding the national problem. Seventhly, it signals a gloomy future. In the 1990s, the economy is growing a little faster than before. However, "even seemingly small deteriorations in overall equity associated with growth can substantially impede progress in alleviating the most severe extremes of poverty in Bangladesh." [18]

Lastly, but not the least, it is a potential source of social conflict and political upheaval. Although so far there has been no organized peasant movement or social conflict originating from the poverty stricken people in the last few decades, it can not be guaranteed in future. Due to the efforts of the government, rate of literacy has been considerably increased. The new generation poverty stricken people with increased awareness of social inequality may not tolerate the status quo. Unless some tangible redistributive measures are taken, the threat of social conflict and violence will continue to loom over the horizon. What is the way out is a big question. In the next section, an attempt will be made to examine some of the proposals put forward by different approaches of modernization and development.

Diverge Theories of Development and Underdevelopment

Psychological Approach

We will begin with psychological approach which deals with the intrinsic factors of modernization and development. According to this approach, it is the attitude, value, belief, personality, achievement, motive and behavioral conditions that are instrumental in modernization and development. Major contributors to the approach include McClelland, Hagen, Inkeles, Smith, Kahl, Kunkel, Horowitz

and others. McClelland argues that the psychological development, i.e., growth of need for achievement (n Achievement) precedes and presumably causes economic change. He suggests how the 'n Achievement' can be raised and recommends the measures to be taken by the government.[19] Hagen explains why a traditional society is stabilized and perpetuated and argue that it is the personality traits of the people—determined by the child rearing practices by the parents—and withdrawal of status respect of elites which are instrumental in bringing social change.[20] If we consider these viewpoints against the causes and consequences of rural poverty in Bangladesh, we come to the conclusion that the psychological approach has nothing to explain and alleviate rural poverty. Some of its proposition may be true, to some extent, for the case of relative poverty or inequality, but certainly not for the absolute poverty. At best, we can term it as an ideology and not as a scientific efforts to find a solution to developmental problem.

Cultural Approach

According to this approach, the obstacle to development are located in fatalistic out-look, ideology, traditional practices and values. Lipset argues that "structural conditions make development possible; cultural factor determines whether the possibilities become an actuality." [21] Foster maintains that peasants world view is dominated by "the image of limited good." He argues that it is the cognitive orientations of the peasants which determines their behavior and participation in economic growth of the country. According to his thesis, the changing of the peasants view of the limited good is the panacea for development.[22] If we study the cognitive orientation of the household described in section III, we may observe the existence of some of the traits of the image of limited good. However, we do not agree with Foster that it is responsible for their poverty. In addition, the removal of the image will not bring them above the poverty line. Access to education, health, technology, infrastructure, and social

justice and economic opportunities are more important than the cognitive orientation. Oscar Lewis coined the term "culture of poverty" and later it was popularized by Michael Harrington. According to Lewis, the behavioral pattern and values of the lower class are characteristically different from those of the dominant society and culture and this unique pattern of behavior and values are transmitted intergenerationally through socialization and have become the determinant of sub culture of poverty.[23] However, Lewis maintains that all poors do not belong to culture of poverty. According to him, "any movement, be it religious, pacifist or revolutionary, which organizes and gives hope to the poor and effectively promotes solidarity and a sense of identification with large groups, destroys the psychological and social core of the culture of poverty." In that sense, the way of life of the rural poor in Bangladesh can not be described as culture of poverty. They are not alienated from the larger society. They have strong family and village ties. They have strong religious identities as Muslims or Hindus and they prey at the same mosque or temple side by side with their rich neighbors. Their children play with those of the well-offs. The poor man may occasionally enjoy a cup of tea or a cigarette with his rich neighbor. He will vigorously participate in the local Union Council election and might be aware of the national leaders. But the difference is: he does not have the economic resources and social status which his rich neighbor has. He is not a leader, but a follower. If he dares to challenge his neighbor, he will certainly fall from grace and might suffer from innumerable consequences including eviction from the land. Given this scenario, we conclude that Lewis's model of culture of poverty is not applicable to the rural poor in Bangladesh.

Transaction Cost Approach

Based on Oliver Williamson's concept of "transaction cost," Douglass North[24] examines the obstacles to economic growth in context of the political/economic institutional economies in history and

consequent transaction costs that determine economic performance and growth. He maintains that it is the costs of transacting that are the key obstacles that prevent economies and societies from realizing well-being. Without elaborate institutional structures, codified property rights and effective enforcement mechanism, the costs of transacting will be very high resulting in cheating, shirking and opportunism which are characteristics of 'bazaar economies.' On the other hand, in case of personal exchange, characterizing small scale production and local trade, transaction costs are low, but because specialization and division of labour are rudimentary, production costs are high. This explains some of the characteristics of the Bangladesh economy: firstly, expansion of non-farm activities specifically small scale production and local trade and loss of productivity associated with fall in real wages; secondly, limited large scale manufacturing or trading operations. North argues that the rise of impersonal rules and contracts "provide the opportunity for individuals with superior coercive power to enforce the rules to their advantage, regardless of their effects on efficiency resulting in high transaction costs." He maintains that "rulers can seldom afford efficient property rights, since they would offend many of their constituents and hence become more insecure." Consequently, "when rulers wish to promulgate rules on the basis of their efficiency consequences, survival will dictate a different course of action." These explains some of the reality in Bangladesh: (1) why the Land Holding Limitation Order, 1972 did not bring any fruitful outcome; (2) why the Land Reform Ordinance, 1984 does not deal with land reform, but mainly share-cropping only, and none of the provisions could be implemented; (3) why The Loan Arbitration Board act, 1989 (created to protect the rural poor from informal money lenders) could not bring any outcome; (4) why the program of distributing government owned land (*Khash Jami*) among the landless could not be implemented; (5) why the banking system, mostly controlled by the government, is reluctant to provide small loans to the poor whose record of repaying is extra-ordinarily good while it provides billions of Taka to the rich who seldom repays; (6)

when the withdrawal of food subsidy is needed, why the victims are rural poors and not members of the armed forces; and (7) why each parliament soon after its constitution shows enthusiasm to modify the rules regarding privileges of the MPs and ministers. From North's arguments, we understand that the emergence of a government as coercive yet enlightened third party establishing and enforcing the structure of property rights, thus reducing the transaction costs in the market mechanism, is a precondition for economic development and this process of establishment may require several centuries. If North is correct in his predictions, then the rural poor in Bangladesh will remain poor for at least another century. However, Japan, South Korea and Taiwan have successfully demonstrated that there are shortcut ways of eliminating poverty and achieving growth.

Dependency Approach

Frank's model of underdevelopment[25] divides the system, both world and national, into two categories: metropolis and periphery. The model asserts that the peripheral countries had been incorporated into world economic system since the early days of colonization. This incorporation transformed the peripheral economies into capitalist economies in a metropolis-peripheral chain under which economic surpluses generated at the periphery are expropriated by the metropolis. This relationship will consistently generate development at the metropolis and underdevelopment at the periphery. The same chain may also be observed within a peripheral economy. according to this model, the rural sector is being exploited by the urban sector. The urban centers within the country are developing by expropriating the economic surpluses of the rural sector. On the other hand, the national economy is being exploited by the world metropolis. So, there is no chance of real economic development in the countries like Bangladesh which have only two options: (1) continue to underdevelop within the chain, or (2) break the chain through social revolution. If we analyze the situation in Bangladesh, we observe the existence of continuing

expropriation both within the country and within the World. However, in a complex interdependent present day society or the World, it is quite impossible to generate economic development by isolationist policy. This will amount to going back to the primitive self sufficient village system. On the other hand, the past history and present trends suggest that it is also impossible to bring socialist revolution in Bangladesh. At the same time, we have noticed institutional shortcomings within the national boundary. Blaming the metropolis-periphery chain and suggesting a social revolution can not solve the problems of poverty in Bangladesh. Especially when many countries have achieved economic development and successfully alleviated poverty within the system, and signs of development can be seen in Bangladesh too, although *dependentistas* term such development as dependent development,[26] we have to look for alternative ways.

Modern World System Theory

This theory divides the world economic system into two extreme poles with an intermediate category: core, periphery and semi-periphery. It is maintained that the world economic system is characterized by unequal exchange and dominance of world means of production by core countries. It is asserted that international structure of inequality is of prime importance and internal socio-economic structure is of secondary importance. The peripheral and semi-peripheral countries have been exploited through unequal exchanges between core and periphery which is an outcome of world economy's primary social relations. It is argued that the present core-periphery division of labor is self-producing and perpetuating in nature. It prescribes that the only solution is the establishment of a non-exploitative and socialistic world economic system.[27]

If we apply this theory to the problem of rural poverty in Bangladesh, we find that the problem is of secondary nature. The primary problem lies in the world system. Until and unless the exploitative world system is corrected, there is no hope for improvement in the secondary

problem. Though their arguments sound convincing, there is no possibility of making the world system socialistic in nature. On the other hand, we observe that some of the countries in the World like South Korea and Taiwan have made significant improvement within the system. also it is not prudent to put all the blame on the world system and disregarding self responsibility. Undoubtedly, there are a lot of internal imbalances as we have mentioned earlier, correction of which is as important as the correction of the world system. We will now examine the viewpoint of the prevailing world system, i. e., the neo-classical approach.

Neo-classical Approach

The neo-classical approach of economics is the counterpart of the structural-functional viewpoint of sociology which deals with modernization and development. After the World War II, the field of economics was dominated by growth theories especially Harrod-Domer Model and Rostow's stage theory got prominence. Lack of capital was considered as chief bottleneck to growth and physical capital accumulation and investment was considered as ultimate source of growth providing employment to surplus labor of traditional agriculture. However, very soon their shortcomings became evident and neo-classical approach took new turn.[28] According to this approach, "GNP rises as the result of the long term effects of capital formation, labor force expansion and technological change, which are assumed to take place under conditions of competitive equilibrium,...[and] labor and capital produce equal marginal return in all uses." [29] Policy induced distortions and non-market failures are held responsible for underdevelopment. Markets, prices, and incentives become central. Privatisation, liberalisation and globalization are strongly recommended. World Bank is the champion of the neo-classical approach. Initially it was thought that the problem of poverty is a temporary phenomenon which will get corrected through "trickle down effect" or "Lewsian turning point." However, it

did not happen. Against the back drop of rising mass poverty and dependency onslaught in the 1970s, World Bank took special cognizance of the problem of poverty in the early 1980s. Presently, World Bank takes a cautious stand in considering economic growth as a solution of poverty. It is because, the relation between extent of poverty and GNP per person has been found far from perfect in many countries. Not only that, "the association between economic growth and improvements in education and health has also been imperfect." [30] In the 1990s, World Bank reassesses its policy on poverty and suggests a strategy with two elements: firstly, promoting the productive use of the poor's most abundant asset—labor; secondly, adopting policies that harness market incentives, social and political institutions, infra-structure and technology and ensuring primary health care, family planning, nutrition and primary education for the poor. It recognizes the importance of redistribution of land in reducing poverty but acknowledges the political obstacles to such efforts. [31]

The empirical evidences from Bangladesh, as discussed in the earlier part of this paper, in the same tone of the world bank, suggest that growth does not necessarily contribute to the reduction of poverty. However, the infra-structural development, diffusion of technology, health care, family planning and education positively influences the poverty situation. Here emerge three big questions: (1) how far the quality of labour can be improved by basic social services? (2) does the government have the capability to provide all these services to all the poor? and (3) will the economy be able to absorb the labour force in productive way under the present environment of globalization?

Regarding the first question, we suggest that the quality of labour can be improved by basic social services only to a limited extent which may enable the poor to graduate from extreme poverty to moderate poverty and from moderate poverty to just above the poverty line. To effectuate substantial increase in the quality of labour, much more

efforts will be needed which are directly dependent upon the later questions.

Regarding the second question, we observe that the government does not have the capability, both institutional and financial, to effectively provide such services to all the poor. A recent World Bank study finds that the government has achieved only 39 percent of 1985-95 targets for rural infra-structure development.[32] Most of the projects were financed through ODA. Presently there is a global trend of reduction in ODA and increase in private flows to the LDCs.[33] There is little possibility that the government will be able to attract private capital flows to invest in rural infra-structure or basic social services. Moreover, Bangladesh is a chronic food deficit country. Annual food production is growing at a rate of 3 percent per annum. A recent FAO study observes that if food production grows at the rate of 4 percent per annum, Bangladesh will become self-sufficient in food by the year 2020.[34] This means that until 2020, Bangladesh will have to import food; thus, reducing the resources to provide basic services. Besides the financial problem, the institutional problem, as described in previous section, will continue to inhibit the process.

Regarding the third question, we suggest that the Bangladesh economy may not be able to absorb the labour force in productive use under the prevailing global circumstances. UNDP aptly summarizes the global constraints for LDC development:[35]

- (1) despite the supposedly abundant labour supply and investment opportunities, no more than 0.2 percent transnational investment is directed to the bottom 20 percent of the World's population.
- (2) Real interest rates have been four times higher for poor nations than rich ones. Developing countries paid 17 percent per annum on their foreign debt during the 1980s while the rich nations paid only 4 percent.

- (3) trade barriers are highest for manufactured goods for which the poor countries enjoy a comparative advantage for labour intensive export such as textiles, clothing and footwear.
- (4) the market for agricultural produce is also distorted by import barrier and US\$300 billion a year agricultural subsidies and price supports in industrial countries, reducing the export opportunities.

Under the above global circumstances, the IMF-World Bank induced market liberalization and WTO induced globalization will only create new market opportunities in Bangladesh for manufactures of advanced countries. As such, the capability of the economy to absorb the surplus labor will remain constrained. Moreover, in the past, though it was possible for countries like Japan or South Korea to develop themselves by adopting unbundling approach, any such possibilities will much more difficult for the countries like Bangladesh. Especially, the scope of role of the state to foster economic development have been reduced to a great extent. Not surprisingly, we are very much skeptical about the success of World Bank pursued neo-classical approach towards alleviating poverty and achieving economic development.

Conclusion

The problem of poverty, especially rural poverty, is a matter of prime concern in Bangladesh. It is not surprising that all the plan documents of the government emphasise alleviation of poverty. Magnitude of the problem is evident from the fact that almost half of the rural population live below the poverty line and the poverty situation has remained almost unchanged over the last thirty years with occasional rise and fall of the rate of the poverty depending upon the prevailing circumstances. In our attempt to find the causes of poverty, we observe eleven socio-economic characteristics of the rural poor: landlessness, lack of education, depending upon agricultural and non-agricultural wage labor, victim of decreasing real wages, unemployed

and underemployed, large family size, poor health, prone to natural disaster, exploited by rural elite's, victim of urban biased development and lacking the benefits of infra-structure and technology. Our findings suggest that the rural poverty is inhibiting the growth of the agriculture. Because of stagnant agriculture, industrialization is also seriously handicapped. Persistent rural poverty and failure of manufacturing sector to absorb surplus labour have induced the expansion of the non-farm sector characterized by low productivity and lower real wages, and thus enhancing the poverty base. Perpetuating poverty is significantly contributing to the abnormal growth of population and with rising awareness caused by increased rate of literacy, the threat of social conflict and violence is looming over the horizon.

In our efforts to look for an explanation and solution for the problem, we observe that diverge theories of development and underdevelopment have some merits as well as limitations. We do not find any immediate relevancy in the psychological and cultural approaches to the problem of rural poverty. Some of the observations may be true in case of relative poverty or inequality which is not our immediate concern. Structure of the Bangladeshi rural society and the overwhelming situational problem do not permit any room for psychological or cultural solution. The transaction costs approach provides meaningful explanation of the problem, but too pessimistic in predicting that it will require several centuries to correct the imbalances. However, it provides very useful insights into the nature of the problem. The dependency and modern world system approaches undermine the problem by highlighting external conditions. While we agree that the external environment is of great importance, as suggested by the approaches, we can not wait for the solution of socialistic revolution. At the same time, we do not disregard the importance of internal imbalances. Lastly, we have analyzed that the neo-classical approach toward third world development is self contradictory in nature. While vigorous efforts may some how manage

to halt the further slide in the poverty situation, the eradication, or at least alleviation, of mass poverty will remain illusory unless some alternative measures are taken.

Among the alternative measures, in addition to neo-classical prescription, we suggest the following: (1) correcting the imbalances in the world economic system, if not wholesale, at least for the low income countries; (2) allowing the poor countries to follow unbundling approach in order to avoid the negative impacts of globalization; (3) drastic institutional reform within the country; and (4) adopting equity oriented growth policy and taking redistributive measures, especially effective land reform. The first two are beyond the capability of the national government, but the emergence of a coercive but enlightened government can achieve the last two. In such event, the country as a whole may still remain poor but will certainly be freed from the curse of poverty. If nothing could be done, the status quo will prevail.

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